

METHODS, EXPERIENCES AND SKILLS WHOM ENGLISH TEACHERS AND ALL PEDAGOGUES NEED.

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ABSTRACT. The article describes ways to improve the quality of education of English teachers in general secondary schools through the use of innovative methods.

Keywords: school, innovation, pedagogue-technologist, method, education, upbringing, knowledge, skill, creative, classification, innovation, objective.

INTRODUCTION. Implementation of the developed experiences of pedagogy and achievements in education is one of the important conditions of today. Currently, a huge base of experience that a teacher can use during his career has been formed, and it is getting richer every day. But despite this, it is difficult for teachers and future professionals to master these experiences . The role of the teacher is particularly important in creating best practices and popularizing them among colleagues. Educators should consider the cost and effectiveness of new pedagogical practices when implementing them. oh the orientation of the teacher's practical activity to innovation provides an opportunity to put into practice the achievements achieved as a result of theoretical pedagogical research. In order to popularize the results of such studies, it is necessary to introduce them to the general public. Providing quick advice on such news by industry experts, a special seminar and it can be conveyed to representatives of other pedagogies by conducting trainings, making presentations at conferences, and giving future pedagogues a series of lectures .

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

At this point, a question arises: "Who are the communicators and promoters of advanced pedagogical ideas and technologies to the general public?" Professors of higher education institutions, senior pedagogues working in universities play an important role in researching and popularizing the experience of a particular pedagogue or educational institution. The reason for this can be explained as follows:

- the author of the innovation cannot give a necessary and accurate assessment of the prospect of a particular pedagogical idea or innovation;
- advanced pedagogues do not always think about popularizing their ideas. The reason is that innovation requires additional time and labor of the pedagogue;
- the idea is not always scientifically and methodologically justified by its creator;
- the authors face obstacles related to the individual characteristics of themselves and their colleagues in describing their innovations and ways of their implementation;
- the task of not only promoting and popularizing pedagogical innovations, but also making corrections to the quality of pedagogues based on them, enriching the professional knowledge and skills of future teachers, is assigned to the creative group;
- the tasks of systematic selection of innovations, monitoring, evaluation of innovative ideas, technologies, enriching the work experience of higher educational institutions are also carried out by the members of the creative group.

The author of the innovative idea does not participate in the management of activities aimed at implementation. This kind of approach creates a basis for expanding the capabilities of an innovative pedagogue and directing him to a specific goal. In this way, the powers of the founder and popularizer of innovative pedagogy are concentrated in one point and directed towards a certain goal. Pedagogical innovation has its own dimensions. Pedagogical innovation consists of the following dimensions that shape the creative activity of the future teacher: how new the

innovative methods are; its optimality; how effective; possibility of application in mass experiment and so on. The main measure of innovative methods is their novelty, it is equal to the results of scientific research and advanced pedagogical experiences. For this reason, taking action in the innovation process

DISCUSSION

An experiment may be new to one teacher, but not new to another. In addition, the level of novelty of the same method may be different for future pedagogues. Taking this into account, both future pedagogues and teachers working in the educational system should approach innovative creative activities based on their own needs.

According to the level of innovation, innovative methods that help to develop the creative functions of future pedagogues are manifested in several forms: absolute level; local-absolute level; conditional degree; subjective level. Public use of innovative pedagogical innovations is interpreted as a criterion for their evaluation. This is mainly related to the technical support of the educational process and the uniqueness of the teacher's activity .

The creative application of pedagogical innovations in mass pedagogical experiments is manifested at the initial stage of the work of individual teachers. These innovations are presented for public use after being tested and objectively evaluated. It is desirable to develop the creative functions of future teachers using innovative methods that are widely popular and allow to achieve positive results. Diagnostic methods aimed at studying the innovative activity of the teacher are also diverse. The use of diagnostic methods shows the strengths of the teacher's activity [20]. Therefore, equipping future teachers with modern methods of diagnosis is the demand of the times. Taking into account the professional needs and desires of the future pedagogues, it is necessary to form a professional and pedagogical ethics in them and carry out full purpose activities aimed at continuous development.

THE RESULT

When studying pedagogical innovations on the basis of diagnosis, one should not forget the need to take into account the presence of positive, developing situations as well as negative manifestations in the experience of each pedagogue. In order for a young pedagogue to work effectively in an educational institution, it is necessary to clearly demonstrate the positive and negative aspects of his work experience on the basis of diagnosis. Innovative it is necessary to clearly convey to the mind of future teachers that the diagnostic methods used for the purpose of studying the processes are as follows.

- systematic study of future teachers' pedagogical needs, interests, areas of particular importance, identifying difficulties encountered in teachers' activities and the possibilities of their elimination;
- search for ideas, concepts and advanced pedagogical experiences that serve to satisfy their interests and needs and introduce them into the practice of higher pedagogical education;
- to determine the originality of future teachers in the process of mastering and applying pedagogical innovations and their various manifestations, in which to demonstrate, describe, hold open classes, work on new resources, such as organizing lectures, participation in experimental work, and wide use of types of work. Based on the diagnosis of pedagogical innovations, it is recommended to carry out practical work aimed at learning in several stages. Questionnaire inquiries from future teachers at the initial stage, examination of the answers to the questionnaire questions, organization of individual interviews and confirmation of the information in the answers to the questionnaire questions, information obtained based on the results of the diagnosis data analysis. At this stage, based on the results of the first stage, activities aimed at improving the future teacher's professional-pedagogical qualification will be planned and the ways of their implementation will be shown. At this stage, the work carried out is completed and repeated diagnosis is carried out. In this process, the future teacher is directed to receive intermediate and final results. The changes in the students' activities in the group are analyzed in depth. As a result

of this, it is necessary to diagnose the professional skills, qualifications and experiences of future teachers and equip them with diagnostic methods, as well as to make the process of professional pedagogical education innovative. reconstruction based on ideas allows effective development of creative activity of students. As a result, there is an opportunity to encourage future teachers to be creative and take initiative .

The creative pedagogical activity of the teacher is the process of positively solving tasks subordinated to the formation of human consciousness and behavior, and most importantly, to the creation of a generation of well-rounded people. Also, the planned learning goal is easily realized and the expected result is achieved faster. That is;

- it is necessary to clearly define the role and tasks of the teacher in the system of innovative educational technology;
- the teacher should be promoted to a new professional position - "teacher-technologist", - "pedagogue-technologist";
- "teacher-technologist" must have special knowledge, skills, qualifications;
- It is necessary to take concrete measures to ensure the prestige, potential increase, spiritual and material interests of the "teacher-technologist" among the pedagogical team.

In order to improve the quality of education, the use of innovative technologies by teachers in the course of the lesson will definitely give effective results.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in order to educate mature specialists who have a high level of general professional culture, social activity, independent thinking, and the ability to solve their tasks without difficulty, today our pedagogic teachers use modern and innovative pedagogical technologies. they should understand that it is the main factor of increasing the quality and efficiency of education, and that it is required by the times.

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